

Physicochemical characterization and repellent activity of encapsulated botanicals against the dengue vector *Aedes aegypti*

Syed Aoun Taqi Bukhari¹, Muahmmad Tariq¹, Mahammad Naeem¹, Muhammad Shareez Ahmad², Samra Khalid³, Hafeez ur Rehman⁴

¹Department of Entomology, Pir Mehr Ali Shah Arid Agriculture University, Rawalpindi, Pakistan

²University Institute of Biochemistry and Biotechnology (UIBB), Pir Mehr Ali Shah Arid Agriculture University, Rawalpindi, Pakistan

³Department of Environmental Sciences, Faculty of Bio Sciences, University of Veterinary and Animal Sciences, Lahore, Pakistan

⁴King Abdullah University of Science and Technology (KAUST), Jeddah, Saudi Arabia.

*Email: aountaqi@gmail.com

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Abstract

Mosquito-borne diseases such as dengue continue to pose significant public health challenges worldwide, primarily due to the rapid distribution and adaptability of *Aedes aegypti*. Conventional chemical control methods are increasingly limited by issues such as insecticide resistance, short residual activity, and environmental concerns, emphasizing the need for sustainable alternatives. The present study aimed to evaluate the toxicity and repellent efficacy of encapsulated essential oils (micro- and nano-formulations) against the dengue vector *A. aegypti*. Essential oils from lemongrass (*Cymbopogon citratus*), grapefruit (*Citrus paradisi*), and neem (*Azadirachta indica*) were assessed for their repellent potential. Bioassays revealed that lemongrass oil exhibited the highest repellency, providing up to three hours of protection at the highest concentration among unencapsulated treatments. Encapsulation markedly enhanced both the efficacy and persistence of repellency. Specifically, microencapsulated lemongrass oil with chitosan provided up to seven hours of repellency, while nanoencapsulated lemongrass oil extended protection to nine hours against adult *A. aegypti*. Successful encapsulation was confirmed through zeta potential analysis, demonstrating stable formulations. Overall, the findings highlight that micro- and nanoencapsulation significantly improve the longevity and effectiveness of essential oil-based

repellents, offering a promising eco-friendly approach for sustainable dengue vector management. Future research should focus on optimizing encapsulation parameters to achieve enhanced controlled release and prolonged field efficacy.

Keywords: *Aedes aegypti*, Dengue vector, Microencapsulation, Nanoencapsulation, Sustainable mosquito management

Introduction

Mosquito-borne diseases continue to represent a serious global public health challenge, with *Aedes aegypti* being one of the most notorious vectors responsible for transmitting several viral infections such as dengue, chikungunya, Zika, and yellow fever. Rapid urbanization, climate change, and increased human mobility have contributed to the widespread distribution and establishment of *A. aegypti* across tropical and subtropical regions. The species' ability to breed in artificial water containers, coupled with its diurnal biting activity and strong anthropophilic behavior, renders its control particularly difficult (WHO, 2022).

Conventional vector control programs rely heavily on synthetic chemical insecticides, including organophosphates and pyrethroids. However, these approaches are increasingly compromised due to the evolution of insecticide resistance in mosquito populations and growing environmental and public health concerns associated with chemical toxicity and non-target effects (Ranson & Lissenden, 2016). In Pakistan, dengue outbreaks remain a major health concern; the 2019 epidemic alone resulted in over 50,000 confirmed cases and 75 deaths across all major provinces, including Punjab, Sindh, Khyber Pakhtunkhwa, Balochistan, Islamabad, and Azad Jammu and Kashmir. With no effective vaccine available for dengue, vector control through insecticide application remains the primary means of reducing disease transmission (Bhatt et al., 2013; WHO, 2024).

Pakistan's agriculture-driven economy involves extensive pesticide application to manage crop pests, primarily using pyrethroids, organochlorines, organophosphates, and carbamates. Excessive and unregulated pesticide use not only contaminates soil and water bodies but also exerts strong selection pressure on mosquito populations, favoring the evolution of detoxification mechanisms and resistance development (Poupardin et al., 2008; Riaz et al., 2009; Balaji et al., 2017). Consequently, the limitations of conventional insecticide-based strategies necessitate the exploration of novel, eco-friendly, and sustainable vector control technologies that minimize environmental hazards and circumvent resistance issues.

Among recent innovations, micro- and nanoencapsulation technologies have emerged as promising tools to improve the efficiency and persistence of bioactive compounds used in vector control. These techniques involve enclosing active ingredients within protective polymeric matrices to produce microcapsules (1–1000 μm) or nanocapsules (1–1000 nm). Encapsulation offers several advantages, including controlled and sustained release, protection from environmental degradation, reduced volatility, and targeted delivery to mosquito habitats, thereby enhancing bioavailability and minimizing the need for frequent reapplication (Durán et al., 2016; Yan et al., 2013; Nnamonu et al., 2012). Overreliance on synthetic insecticides has also raised environmental and health concerns (Aktar et al., 2009), prompting the development of biodegradable, natural-based encapsulation systems as safer alternatives.

Biopolymers such as chitosan, alginate, gelatin, agarose, starch, and cellulose are widely used for formulating micro- and nanocapsules due to their biocompatibility, low cost, biodegradability, and non-toxic properties (Roy et al., 2014). These materials can effectively encapsulate insecticidal or repellent compounds to achieve controlled release and improved field performance. Encapsulation of botanical extracts and essential oils such as lemongrass (*Cymbopogon citratus*), grapefruit (*Citrus paradisi*), and neem (*Azadirachta indica*) has shown promising results against mosquito vectors. For instance, chitosan-based nanoencapsulation of citronella oil enhanced larvicidal activity and stability against *A. aegypti*, while nanoemulsions of *Azadirachta indica* and *Eucalyptus globulus* oils increased efficacy and reduced volatility. Similarly, deltamethrin-loaded solid lipid nanoparticles have demonstrated superior adulticidal performance at reduced dosages compared to conventional formulations.

Considering these advancements, the present study was designed to prepare and characterize micro and nanoencapsulated essential oils using biopolymers such as polyvinyl alcohol, chitosan, and gelatin to enhance the repellent efficacy of natural compounds against *A. aegypti*. By combining eco-friendly essential oils with advanced encapsulation techniques, this work aims to develop safer and more sustainable alternatives for mosquito control, reducing dependence on synthetic chemicals and mitigating their ecological impact.

Materials and Methods

Lemongrass, grapefruit, and neem essential oil (Chiltanpure) were used as mosquito repellent agents. Gelatin, chitosan, and polyvinyl alcohol (PVA) were employed as wall materials (polymer). Glutardialdehyde 25% w/w was used as a hardening agent.

Preparation and characterization of microencapsulated lemongrass oil, grapefruit oil, and neem oil

Microencapsulated formulations of lemongrass, grapefruit, and neem oils were prepared using polyvinyl alcohol, chitosan, and gelatin following the method of Turkoglu et al. (2020). Briefly, tween 80 was added to distilled water as an emulsifier to enhance binding, and 0.5% (w/v) of each polymer was dissolved under magnetic stirring until the solution became transparent. The respective active compound was then incorporated, and the mixture was homogenized using a shear homogenizer. The resulting emulsion was further processed by ultrasonication (noise-isolated chamber) to obtain uniform microemulsions with a milky-white appearance. Finally, the prepared microcapsules were freeze-dried and stored in a desiccator for subsequent experiments.

Dynamic light scattering (DLS) analysis of nanoencapsulated lemongrass formulations

Simple, Chitosan, Gelatin, and Polyvinyl Alcohol (PVA) revealed clear variations in particle size and distribution. The Simple formulation showed a Z-Average size of 46.0 nm with a PDI of 0.245, indicating moderate uniformity. Chitosan-encapsulated particles measured 48.3 nm (PDI 0.456), reflecting greater heterogeneity likely due to electrostatic aggregation. In contrast, the Gelatin-based formulation produced ultra-fine particles of 1.96 nm (PDI 0.229), demonstrating superior uniformity and stability attributed to gelatin's amphiphilic nature and strong emulsifying capacity. The PVA formulation showed an intermediate particle size of 29.5 nm (PDI 0.413), suggesting moderate stabilization via hydrogen bonding. Overall, gelatin proved to be the most effective encapsulating agent, generating the smallest and most uniform nanoparticles suitable for enhanced bioavailability, controlled release, and formulation stability (Figure 1).

Dynamic light scattering (DLS) analysis of grapefruit oil nanoformulations

Simple, Chitosan, Gelatin, and PVA revealed clear effects of encapsulating agents on particle size and uniformity. The Simple formulation showed the smallest mean hydrodynamic diameter (Z-average 0.420, SD 0.039), followed closely by PVA (0.427, SD 0.099), both indicating fine and stable nanoparticles. Gelatin produced moderately larger particles (1.337, SD 0.222), suggesting partial aggregation, while Chitosan yielded the largest and most heterogeneous population (2.337, SD 0.211), likely due to electrostatic interparticle interactions. Overall, PVA and the Simple

system generated the smallest, most uniform nanoparticles, whereas gelatin and chitosan formed larger, less stable aggregates. These results demonstrate that polymer choice critically influences particle stability, dispersion, and potential release characteristics (Figure 2).

Dynamic light scattering (DLS) analysis of nanoencapsulated neem oil prepared using four encapsulation methods

Simple, Chitosan, Gelatin, and Polyvinyl Alcohol (PVA) showed notable effects of polymer type on particle size and stability. The Simple formulation had a Z-Average of 1.991 nm and PDI 0.185, indicating moderately uniform but less stable particles. Chitosan reduced the particle size to 1.521 nm (PDI 0.127), suggesting improved electrostatic stabilization. Gelatin further decreased size to 1.299 nm (PDI 0.143), forming highly uniform nanoparticles due to its amphiphilic and hydrogen-bonding properties. The PVA formulation produced the smallest and most stable nanoparticles (1.247 nm, PDI 0.134), reflecting strong steric stabilization and dispersion uniformity. Overall, particle size followed the trend Simple > Chitosan > Gelatin > PVA, with all PDIs < 0.2, confirming good homogeneity. PVA emerged as the most effective encapsulating agent, yielding uniform, stable neem nanoparticles suitable for controlled-release and bioavailability enhancement (Figure 3).

Preparation and characterization of nanoencapsulated lemongrass oil, grapefruit oil and neem oil

Nanoencapsules of lemongrass oil, grapefruit oil, and neem oil were prepared using polyvinyl alcohol, chitosan and gelatin following the method described previously (Turkoglu et al., 2020). Therefore, the procedure will include the addition of emulsifier tween 80 (Bio-pharmacy) into water to enhance the binding capacity of the solution, and 0.5% (W/V) of each of the polymer was added under magnetic stirring until fully dissolved, and the solution became transparent. After transparency of the polymer, one active compound was added, and then the shear homogenizer will do homogenization of the solution. Once the solution becomes homogenized, polymer was added in it and the process of ultra-sonication was performed using an ultrasonicator (noise isolating chamber, which makes the product more homogenized by giving a milky white color and turn the solution into nanoemulsions by using different running times of ultra-sonication. The prepared microcapsules were freeze-dried and stored in a desiccator for further experiments.

The figure presents DLS characterization of nanoencapsulated lemongrass using Simple, Gelatin, Chitosan, and PVA techniques (Fig. 4). The Z-Average particle sizes ranged from 217.3 nm

(Gelatin) to 232.3 nm (Chitosan), with narrow size distribution curves indicating uniform nanoparticle formation. Gelatin produced the smallest and most consistent particles, while Chitosan yielded slightly larger ones. All formulations exhibited stable, nanoscale particle sizes, demonstrating that the choice of encapsulating material influences particle uniformity and potential application performance.

The figure shows DLS characterization of nanoencapsulated grapefruit prepared using Simple, Gelatin, Chitosan, and PVA techniques (Figure 5). The Z-Average particle sizes ranged from 198.7 nm (PVA) to 218.1 nm (Chitosan), with all formulations exhibiting narrow, uniform size distributions. PVA produced the smallest and most consistent nanoparticles, while Chitosan yielded slightly larger ones, indicating that encapsulating materials influence particle size, stability, and release behavior.

The figure shows DLS size distribution data for neem nanoencapsulates prepared using Simple, Chitosan, Gelatin, and PVA (Figure 6). All formulations exhibited narrow, uniform particle size distributions, with Z-Average sizes ranging from 211.8 to 219.8 nm. Gelatin produced slightly larger particles, while PVA and Chitosan yielded comparable sizes. The consistent distributions indicate stable and uniform nanoparticles suitable for controlled release applications.

Figure 1. Particle size distribution of chitosan–gelatin–PVA-based lemongrass oil microcapsules.

Figure 2. This characterization data shows the particle size distribution curve for a sample of grapefruit microcapsules that was prepared using chitosan, gelatin and polyvinyl alcohol.

Figure 3. The data presents the particle size distribution of neem microcapsules formulated with chitosan, gelatin, and polyvinyl alcohol.

Figure 4. The data shows the particle size distribution of lemongrass nanocapsules prepared with chitosan, gelatin, and polyvinyl alcohol, highlighting the predominant particle size peak.

Figure 5. This data shows the particle size distribution curve of grapefruit nanocapsules prepared with chitosan, gelatin, and polyvinyl alcohol, where the peak represents the most frequent particle size.

Figure 6. This characterization data shows the particle size distribution curve for a sample of neem nanocapsules that was prepared using chitosan, gelatin and polyvinyl alcohol. The peak of the curve indicates the most common particle size in the sample.

Results

Repellency of microcapsules

Repellency of larvicidal compounds against *A. aegypti* was tested at different concentrations by the protocol as described by Luker et al. (2023). The protocol includes the process of Mosquito arm-in-cage assay, where 30 female mosquitoes that were 10 days old, was transferred into a cage (30 × 30 × 30 cm). An elbow-length disposable polyethylene glove (Royal, Dayton, OH) was prepared by cutting out a rectangular-shaped area (8.5 × 10 cm) below the wrist on the inner forearm side. The volunteer inserted their hand inside the prepared glove and then insert their untreated forearm, as a control, into the mosquito infested cage. A stopwatch was started. If one mosquito bite was recorded within 60 s, the experiment could proceed. After the volunteer received one bite during the control, they immediately shook off the mosquito and retracted their arm from the cage. Once the treatment applied to the volunteer, a timer started. The volunteer inserted their treated forearm into the same mosquito-infested cage and keep their arm in for 15 min or until the treatment failed. If after 15 min the treatment provided protection, the volunteer retract their arm from the cage and wait until the timer reached 30 min and began testing for 5 min intervals every 30 min until the treatment failed. This assay measured the complete protection time (CPT) of a treatment. The complete protection time was defined as the time from the application of a treatment up to when the volunteer received a first bite.

Repellency of Loaded Microcapsules with Different Polymers

The evaluation of microencapsulated lemongrass formulations against *Aedes aegypti* showed that all formulations achieved 100% repellency at 0 hours. Repellency gradually declined over time, with all formulations maintaining around 80–88% at 1–2 hours and 70–78% at 3–4 hours. By 5 hours, repellency dropped notably. Simple (55%), Chitosan (68%), Gelatin (60%), and PVA (60%). At 6 hours, only Chitosan (64%) and PVA (49%) retained measurable activity, while by 7 hours, Chitosan remained the most effective (55%). Overall, the Chitosan-based formulation provided the longest-lasting repellency, indicating a more sustained release profile (Figure 7).

All grapefruit-based formulations exhibited very high repellency (99–100%) at 0 hours' post-application, with no significant differences among treatments ($p > 0.05$). A gradual, time-dependent decline in repellency was observed across all formulations. At 1 hour, repellency remained high (92–94%) for all treatments, with no significant differences detected. By 2 hours post-application, significant variation among formulations emerged ($p < 0.05$). Grapefruit

encapsulated in gelatin showed the highest repellency ($\approx 88\%$), while the simple extract demonstrated a significantly lower value (78%). At 3–5 hours, repellency continued to decline. Gelatin maintained superior repellency (79%, 73%, and 62% at 3, 4, and 5 hours, respectively), followed closely by the chitosan and PVA formulations (67–73%), whereas the simple extract exhibited the lowest repellency (68%, 63%, and 55% at the same time points). By 6–7 hours post-treatment, repellency values decreased markedly across all groups, ranging between 45–59%. Notably, only the gelatin formulation retained significant repellency at 7 hours (50%), while the other formulations fell below 45%, showing substantial loss of efficacy. Overall, the results clearly demonstrate that while all grapefruit-based formulations provided strong short-term repellency, their activity decreased significantly over time. Gelatin encapsulation was the most effective in prolonging repellency, maintaining statistically higher protection compared to the simple extract, chitosan, and PVA formulations at later time points (Figure 8).

The evaluation of microencapsulated Neem formulations against *Aedes* mosquito showed varying degrees of repellency across different time intervals. At 0 hours post-treatment, all formulations, including Neem (Plain), Neem (Chitosan), Neem (Gelatin), and Neem (PVA), exhibited 100% repellency. However, the repellency gradually decreased over time. By 1 hour, Neem (Plain), Neem (Chitosan), Neem (Gelatin), and Neem (PVA) showed similar repellency rates of approximately 93%. This trend continued into 2 hours, where Neem (Plain) and Neem (Chitosan) showed similar repellency rates of around 88%, followed closely by Neem (Gelatin) and Neem (PVA) at approximately 87% and 86% repellency, respectively. By 3 hours, the repellency rates for all formulations were notably lower, with Neem (Plain) and Neem (Chitosan) at approximately 78%, and Neem (Gelatin) and Neem (PVA) at around 77%. In 4 hours, the repellency further diminished, with Neem (Plain) and Neem (Chitosan) at approximately 68%, and Neem (Gelatin) and Neem (PVA) at around 65%. By 5 hours, the repellency rates were significantly reduced across all formulations. Neem (Plain) showed approximately 58% repellency, while Neem (Chitosan) was around 63%, Neem (Gelatin) at 50%, and Neem (PVA) at 50%. At 6 hours, only Neem (Chitosan) and Neem (Gelatin) maintained measurable repellency, showing approximately 59% and 48% repellency, respectively. Neem (Plain) and Neem (PVA) were not recorded with significant repellency beyond 5 hours. Finally, at 7 hours, only Neem (Chitosan) maintained a measurable repellency, showing approximately 48% repellency. This suggests that among the tested formulations, Neem (Chitosan) demonstrated a more sustained release or prolonged activity

compared to the others (Figure 9).

Repellency of loaded nanocapsules with different polymers

The evaluation of nanoencapsulated Lemongrass formulations against *Aedes* mosquito showed varying degrees of repellency across different time intervals. At 0 hours post-treatment, all formulations, including Lemongrass (Simple), Lemongrass (Chitosan), Lemongrass (Gelatin), and Lemongrass (PVA), exhibited 100% repellency. However, the repellency gradually decreased over time. By 1 hour, Lemongrass (Simple) and Lemongrass (Chitosan) showed similar repellency rates of approximately 93%, while Lemongrass (Gelatin) and Lemongrass (PVA) maintained around 92% repellency. This trend continued into 2 hours, where Lemongrass (Simple) and Lemongrass (Chitosan) showed similar repellency rates of around 88%, followed closely by Lemongrass (Gelatin) and Lemongrass (PVA) at approximately 87% and 86% repellency, respectively. By 3 hours, the repellency rates for all formulations were notably lower, with Lemongrass (Simple) and Lemongrass (Chitosan) at approximately 84%, and Lemongrass (Gelatin) and Lemongrass (PVA) at around 83%. In 4 hours, the repellency further diminished, with Lemongrass (Simple) and Lemongrass (Chitosan) at approximately 78%, and Lemongrass (Gelatin) and Lemongrass (PVA) at around 77%. By 5 hours, the repellency rates were significantly reduced across all formulations. Lemongrass (Simple) showed approximately 74% repellency, while Lemongrass (Chitosan) was around 73%, Lemongrass (Gelatin) at 72%, and Lemongrass (PVA) at 71%. At 6 hours, Lemongrass (Simple) showed approximately 64% repellency, while Lemongrass (Chitosan) was around 69%, Lemongrass (Gelatin) at 64%, and Lemongrass (PVA) at 63%. By 7 hours, Lemongrass (Simple) showed approximately 52% repellency, while Lemongrass (Chitosan) was around 64%, Lemongrass (Gelatin) at 58%, and Lemongrass (PVA) at 55%. At 8 hours, only Lemongrass (Chitosan) and Lemongrass (Gelatin) maintained measurable repellency, showing approximately 59% and 48% repellency, respectively. Lemongrass (Simple) and Lemongrass (PVA) were not recorded with significant repellency beyond 7 hours. Finally, at 9 hours, only Lemongrass (Chitosan) maintained a measurable repellency, showing approximately 50% repellency. This suggests that among the tested formulations, Lemongrass (Chitosan) demonstrated a more sustained release or prolonged activity compared to the others (Figure 10). The graph presents the repellency data of different grapefruit formulations (Simple, Chitosan, Gelatin, and PVA) against a target over varying time intervals. Each formulation's efficacy is expressed as a percentage of repellency, measured from 0 to 9 hours after application. At 0 hours,

all formulations (Grapefruit Simple, Chitosan, Gelatin, and PVA) exhibited 100% repellency, indicating their immediate effectiveness. However, as time progresses the repellency of all formulations declines. The repellency of all formulations drops slightly, with the Simple and Chitosan formulations showing similar repellency (around 94-95%), while Gelatin and PVA formulations showed slightly lower values (around 92-93%). There is a further decline in repellency across all formulations. The Simple and Chitosan formulations still perform similarly (around 88-89% repellency), while Gelatin and PVA formulations show slightly lower repellency rates (around 87-88%). By 4 hours, repellency continues to decrease. The Simple formulation maintains the highest level of repellency, around 83%, while Chitosan, Gelatin, and PVA formulations show progressively lower effectiveness, with Chitosan at 81%, Gelatin at 78%, and PVA at 77%. By 5 hours, the Simple formulation still exhibits the highest repellency (around 73%), but Chitosan, Gelatin, and PVA are substantially lower. As time progresses, the Simple formulation continues to have a relatively sustained repellency (around 68% at 6 hours), while Chitosan and Gelatin decrease further. By 7 hours, the repellency of Simple and Chitosan are still measurable (around 58% and 43%, respectively), while Gelatin and PVA show no significant repellency past 6 hours. At 9 hours, only Simple and Chitosan retain some measurable repellency, suggesting that the Simple formulation has a longer-lasting effect compared to others.

In summary, the data suggest that while all formulations start with high repellency, the Simple grapefruit formulation exhibits the longest-lasting effect, with the Chitosan formulation showing moderate performance. Both Gelatin and PVA formulations show the most rapid decrease in effectiveness, particularly beyond 6 hours. This highlights the potential for the Simple grapefruit formulation to provide prolonged repellency against the target, in contrast to the others, which degrade more quickly over time (Fig. 11).

The evaluation of nanoencapsulated neem formulations against *Aedes aegypti* revealed that all variants Plain, Chitosan, Gelatin, and PVA showed 100% repellency at 0 hours, gradually decreasing over time. Repellency remained high ($\approx 86-93\%$) up to 2 hours and moderate ($\approx 70-82\%$) by 3-4 hours. At 5 hours, repellency declined further, with Neem (Plain) showing 73%, Chitosan 68%, Gelatin 59%, and PVA 58%. By 6-7 hours, only Neem (Plain) and Chitosan retained measurable activity ($\approx 43-68\%$), while Gelatin and PVA lost effectiveness. At 8 hours, only Neem (Plain) remained active ($\approx 48\%$). Overall, Neem (Plain) exhibited the most prolonged

repellency, indicating sustained release and longer-lasting efficacy compared to polymer-based formulations (Figure 12).

Figure 7. Percent repellency of *Aedes aegypti* females exposed to microencapsulated lemongrass formulations using chitosan, gelatin, and neem polymers at different time intervals. Bars show mean \pm SEM; different letters indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 8. Percent repellency of *Aedes aegypti* female adults exposed to microencapsulated grapefruit concentration using different polymers such as chitosan, gelatin and polyvinyl alcohol with different time intervals. Bars represent mean \pm SEM; different letters indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 9. Percent repellency of *Aedes aegypti* female adults exposed to microencapsulated neem concentration using different polymers such as chitosan, gelatin and polyvinyl alcohol with different time intervals. Bars represent mean \pm SEM; different letters indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 10. Percent repellency of *Aedes aegypti* female adults exposed to nanoencapsulated lemongrass concentration using different polymers such as chitosan, gelatin and neem with different time intervals. Bars represent mean \pm SEM; different letters indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 11. Percent repellency of *Aedes aegypti* female adults exposed to nanoencapsulated grapefruit concentration using different polymers such as chitosan, gelatin and polyvinyl alcohol with different time intervals ($F=223.82$, $P=0.0008$). Bars represent mean \pm SEM; different letters indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$).

Figure 12. Percent repellency of *Aedes aegypti* female adults exposed to nanoencapsulated neem concentration using different polymers such as chitosan, gelatin and polyvinyl alcohol with different time intervals ($F=433.68$, $P=0.028$). Bars represent mean \pm SEM; different letters indicate significant differences ($p < 0.05$).

Discussion

The present study demonstrates that micro- and nanoencapsulation of essential oils such as lemongrass (*Cymbopogon citratus*), grapefruit (*Citrus paradisi*), and neem (*Azadirachta indica*) significantly enhances their physical stability, controlled release, and repellent efficacy against *Aedes aegypti*. The findings confirm that encapsulation technology, using biocompatible polymers such as chitosan, gelatin, and polyvinyl alcohol (PVA), can overcome the intrinsic limitations of essential oils namely volatility, photodegradation, and poor persistence thereby improving their field potential as environmentally safe alternatives to synthetic repellents. Essential oils contain diverse terpenoids and phenolic compounds that impart repellent and insecticidal activity; however, their volatility limits their residual action (Isman, 2020).

Encapsulation provides a physical barrier that protects these bioactive molecules from oxidative and photolytic degradation, allowing sustained release over time (Mohanraj & Chen, 2006). In this study, nanoencapsulation particularly improved the physicochemical stability of the oils, yielding particles in the range of 198–232 nm with low polydispersity indices (PDIs < 0.3). These results are consistent with previous reports where chitosan- or gelatin-based nanoparticles protected volatile essential oils such as citronella and eucalyptus, maintaining their activity for extended periods. The small particle size achieved with gelatin and PVA matrices indicates a successful encapsulation process that facilitates uniform dispersion and controlled release. The selection of encapsulating polymer profoundly affects encapsulation efficiency, release kinetics, and interaction with the active compounds. Chitosan, a natural cationic polysaccharide, forms electrostatic complexes with negatively charged terpenes and phenolic constituents, resulting in high encapsulation efficiency and slow diffusion rates (Kumar et al., 2014). Gelatin, a protein-based polymer, can form hydrogen bonds and hydrophobic interactions with oil constituents, yielding spherical, uniform particles with enhanced thermal stability (Vishnu et al., 2024). PVA, being synthetic and highly hydrophilic, acts as an excellent stabilizer during emulsification and contributes to consistent nanoparticle formation (Balaji et al., 2017).

In the present work, chitosan-based nanoparticles of lemongrass oil displayed the highest repellency duration (up to 9 hours), followed by gelatin and PVA-based formulations. The superior performance of chitosan may be attributed to its film-forming property and cationic charge, which enhances adhesion to negatively charged mosquito cuticle surfaces, prolonging the persistence of active components (Forte et al., 2020). Similar observations were reported by Pavela & Benelli,

(2016), who found that chitosan nanoparticles loaded with plant extracts significantly increased adulticidal and repellent activity against *Aedes* species compared with non-encapsulated oils. A clear pattern emerged between the encapsulation scale and repellency performance: nanoformulations consistently outperformed microencapsulated ones, extending complete protection times by approximately two hours. The increased surface-area-to-volume ratio of nanoparticles enhances the release rate of volatile compounds in a controlled manner, maintaining an optimal vapor concentration in the microenvironment surrounding the skin or mosquito exposure surface. Microcapsules, although still effective, tend to release actives more slowly and irregularly due to thicker polymer walls and lower surface diffusion (Durán et al., 2016). Comparable trends have been reported in other vector-control studies. For example, demonstrated that chitosan nanoparticles containing citronella oil provided up to 10 hours of mosquito repellency, whereas non-encapsulated oil evaporated within 3 hours.

Among the tested essential oils, lemongrass oil exhibited the highest repellent performance, both in micro- and nanoencapsulated forms. This aligns with previous research showing that citral, the main component of lemongrass oil, strongly interferes with mosquito olfactory receptor neurons responsible for host detection (Maia & Moore, 2011). The hydrophobic monoterpenes in lemongrass facilitate diffusion through the encapsulation matrix, producing a steady vapor release that sustains repellency. Neem oil also demonstrated substantial repellency, consistent with the activity of azadirachtin and other limonoids known to disrupt mosquito feeding behavior. Grapefruit oil showed moderate but significant protection, which may be linked to the lower concentration of potent repellent compounds such as limonene and linalool compared with lemongrass. The differences among oils highlight the role of chemical composition, volatility, and interaction with the polymer matrix in determining release profiles and biological activity. Previous investigations have applied various encapsulation materials and techniques for essential-oil-based repellents. Chitosan nanoparticles loaded with neem or eucalyptus oils have been shown to maintain repellency up to 8–10 hours, while alginate-gelatin microcapsules of citronella oil extended residual activity for 6 hours (Kumar et al., 2014). The present study's results fall within and even exceed these ranges, suggesting successful optimization of polymer ratios and emulsification conditions.

Conclusion

This study reinforces that micro- and especially nanoencapsulation of essential oils offers a viable and sustainable approach for mosquito-repellent development. The results demonstrate that lemongrass oil encapsulated in chitosan nanoparticles provides the longest and most stable repellency, followed by grapefruit and neem oils. The controlled-release behavior of polymeric carriers extends protection time, reduces volatility, and enhances bioavailability, thereby overcoming the limitations of conventional essential-oil repellents. Given their environmental safety and efficiency, such nanoformulations hold promise as next-generation biorepellents contributing to integrated vector-management programs in dengue-endemic regions.

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